

HEREDITARY

HetERogeneous sEmantic Data integration for the guT-bRain interplaY

Task 3.6

Findability Platforms Landscape

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Executive Summary

This landscape, part of HEREDITARY's Deliverable 3.6, ¹ surveys the main portals, services and platforms we can use to raise the findability of HEREDITARY datasets, comparing each by scope, discovery options, data transfer, cost, and access control.

Based on the analysis, the recommended, low-friction mix is to: (1) submit data/metadata to EGA/FEGA when data transfer is allowed (archival, governance, PIDs...); (2) always publish dataset metadata to HIP (HealthDCAT-AP) and register the catalogue for harvesting by data.europa.eu; (3) create dataset-level Zenodo records, including minimal details and files (e.g., Data Access Policies); (4) use BioStudies for a citable study-level landing page that links to the other records; and (5) expose a Beacon v2 endpoint for federated discovery without centralising data.

This set is EU-aligned, free to use, has human and programmatic discovery, and minimises development overhead while supporting Task 3.6's FAIRification goals and 1+MG/GA4GH practices.

Methodology and limitations. *This landscape was compiled from publicly available documentation and live portals as of October 2025. The authors did not consult most platform developers or maintainers directly to review information. As a result, some details may be incomplete, outdated, or inconsistent. Please report corrections or updates to [mcasado\[at\]ebi.ac.uk](mailto:mcasado[at]ebi.ac.uk).*

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17901862>

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Glossary

Abbreviation	Description
1+MG	1+ Million Genomes initiative
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
AC	Access Control
API	Application Programming Interface
BBMRI-ERIC	Biobanking and BioMolecular resources Research Infrastructure – European Research Infrastructure Consortium
CC0	Creative Commons Zero
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research
COAR	Confederation of Open Access Repositories
CRG	Centre for Genomic Regulation
DaaS	Data-as-a-Service
DAC	Data Access Committee
DCAT-AP	EU profile of DCAT for data catalogues
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPA	Data Processing Agreement
DTA	Data Transfer Agreement
DUO	Data Use Ontology (usage codes)
EFO	Experimental Factor Ontology
EGA	European Genome–phenome Archive
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EHR	Electronic Health Records
ELIXIR	European Life-Science Infrastructure
EMBL-EBI	European Bioinformatics Institute
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive

Abbreviation	Description
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FDP	Fair Data Point (metadata service)
FED	Federated Discovery
FEGA	Federated European Genome–phenome Archive
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
G2MC	Global Genomic Medicine Collaborative
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
GDI	Genome Data Infrastructure
GDPR	EU General Data Protection Regulation
HDN	Hereditary Data Network
HealthDCAT-AP	Health extension of DCAT-AP
HIP	European Health Information Portal
IHCC	International Health Cohorts Consortium
INSDC	International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation (data format)
KGaaS	Knowledge-Graph-as-a-Service
MAGE-TAB	MicroArray Gene Expression Tabular (functional genomics metadata format)
MIABIS	Minimum Information About Biobank Data Sharing
MINSEQE	Minimum Information about a high-throughput SEQuencing Experiment
MQA	Metadata Quality Assessment (data.europa.eu)
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PID	Persistent Identifier

Abbreviation	Description
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDF4J	Java framework for RDF/SPARQL
RDFS	RDF Schema
REST	Representational State Transfer (web API style)
SDK	Software Development Kit
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language (RDF validation)
SNOMED	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine
SNOMED CT	SNOMED Clinical Terminology standard
SP	Submitter Portal
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language (RDF query language/endpoint)
T3.6	Task 3.6 (FAIRification)
UI	User Interface
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
WP	Work Package (project workstream)

Term	Description
Accession	Stable identifier assigned by an archive
Beaconisation	Mapping local metadata to Beacon model and deploying it as an endpoint
DataCite	DOI registration agency
Catalogue (DCAT)	A collection of dataset descriptions
Controlled access	Data access via approvals/policies (e.g., DAC)
Dataset (DCAT)	A describable, citable data resource
Development overhead	Extra technical work, time, and resources needed to build or customise new systems or infrastructure, beyond simply using existing services <i>as is</i> .

Term	Description
FAIRification	Practical steps to make data FAIR
Federated discovery	Query many nodes without moving data
Findability	Ease of discovering datasets/metadata
Harmonisation	Aligning variables/metadata across sources
Harvesting	Pulling metadata from provider catalogues
Metadata-only record	Public description without sharing raw data
Ontology	Controlled concepts/relations for semantics
Persistent identifier	Long-lived, resolvable ID (e.g., DOI/accession)
Phenopackets	GA4GH phenotype data model
Triplestore	Database for RDF triples/graphs

1. Introduction

The HEREDITARY project ⁶ seeks to facilitate **compliance with FAIR principles**, ⁷ ensuring that its datasets are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.

Due to data usage policies or personal preference, overseers of data sources within HEREDITARY have **different approaches to FAIRify their datasets**:

1. Some are able to **transfer the sensitive data itself** (e.g., sequence files) to centralised repositories.
2. Others would favour distributing non-identifiable (meta)data:
 - a. **Metadata-only records** (i.e. dataset descriptions without sharing raw or granular data) that can be used as gateways to the data.
 - b. **Federated discovery** approaches, where pseudonymised data (e.g., a sequence variant) can be discovered without infringing data privacy or requiring granted access.

To **ensure maximal discoverability for all proprietary datasets**, whether data is relocated or remains scattered across sources, HEREDITARY needs to identify the most suitable metadata portals or platforms to use.

In this document, we focus on **discoverability and findability**. For the purpose of this task, the two terms can be used interchangeably, although they are not strictly identical. *Discoverability* refers to the ability of users to encounter new or previously unknown datasets, even without actively searching for them; while *Findability* relates to the ease of locating a dataset once its existence is known. In practice, all findable datasets are discoverable once a user knows what to look for (i.e., something related to the dataset), but not all discoverable datasets meet FAIR standards for findability (e.g., datasets that appear in a catalogue but lack persistent identifiers).

This landscape document **surveys existing services** with respect to their ability to **increase discoverability of datasets**. The aim is to inform which solution(s) will best support Task 3.6 (*FAIRification workflows and 1+MG guidelines compliance*), ⁸ with particular emphasis on clinical and genomic data, both structured and unstructured.

⁶ <https://hereditary-project.eu/overview/>

⁷ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles>

⁸

<https://hereditary-project.eu/making-data-work-for-science-how-hereditary-is-embracing-fair-principles/>

2. Objectives and scope

2.1. What is included

- Portals, platforms, and services which provide (meta)data registration, indexing, or hosting of datasets **relevant to Task 3.6 of the HEREDITARY project**: domains such as biomedical research, genomics, cohorts or clinical health records.
- Both **open-access and controlled-access** solutions, and both **free and commercial** models.
- **Main characteristics of each solution**, including discovery/search interfaces; governance and sustainability; scope of archived or indexed data; programmatic access; costs; and limitations.
- Features relevant to **findability**: metadata standards used, discovery interfaces, ability to index metadata-only records, ability to link data with other resources where possible.
- **Comparison of platforms** as they apply to HEREDITARY's context.

2.2. What is excluded

- Detailed technical deep-dives into storage or compute infrastructure for each solution and/or the project's proprietary data sources.
- Portals that are characteristic of domains outside of HEREDITARY's core data sources, unless justified by their exemplary metadata practices or widespread implementations.
- Full legal/privacy analysis of each solution.

2.3. Perspective

This document is generally written from a **neutral viewpoint**: surveying what is possible in the data discoverability ecosystem. At the same time, it includes **remarks specific to HEREDITARY's data sources**, indicating how each platform or service might align (or not) with project constraints. This is increasingly apparent in the final sections, where we discuss all surveyed approaches with respect to the needs of the HEREDITARY project.

Furthermore, given the overall project's **advocacy for Open Science**, publicly accessible resources with no paywalls are prioritised.

Finally, we acknowledge that most of HEREDITARY's participants and data sources are based in the European Union (EU), and that the project is funded under an EU

framework (Horizon Europe, GA No. 101137074).⁹ Consequently, our survey inherently gives priority to platforms and portals that are compatible with EU policies, standards, and legal/regulatory environments (e.g. GDPR, DCAT-AP). However, we consider the position of non-EU participants (e.g., UCD) for the discussion, with the aim to choose a solution that is applicable across all project partners.

3. Evaluated metadata portals and solutions

For each inspected service we lay out an overview (including a summary table), submission requirements and submission process. For an aggregated view of all options, refer to [Table 22](#).

3.1. European Health Information Portal

3.1.1. Overview

The **Health Information Portal (HIP)** is a recently created **European health data catalogue service** [1]. Its aim is to **make health datasets more visible and interoperable** across Europe's emerging Health Data Space.¹⁰ It serves as the one-stop shop to facilitate access to population health and healthcare data across Europe.¹¹ Furthermore, it has its own **editor (v4.0) and sandbox**,¹² an accessible API to harvest information,¹³ as well as its **ongoing specification** (HealthDCAT-AP Release 5).¹⁴ This portal enables any health data holder to create and publish a dataset metadata record in a format compliant with HealthDCAT-AP,¹⁵ an emerging EU-wide application profile for health dataset catalogues.

The HIP serves as a catalogue not only for data and health information, but also for National Nodes, European Research Networks, Output & Dissemination, Capacity Building Activities and National Research Projects.

The portal was developed through the joint efforts of PHIRI (Population Health Information Research Infrastructure)¹⁶ and the InfAct Joint Action (Information for Action).¹⁷

The portal provides a web-based metadata editor that guides users through describing their dataset with DCAT-AP (v3.0.0)¹⁸ fields (title, description, themes, etc.) plus

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.3030/101137074>

¹⁰

https://health.ec.europa.eu/ehealth-digital-health-and-care/european-health-data-space-regulation-ehds_en

¹¹ <https://www.healthinformationportal.eu/health-information-portal>

¹² <https://ehds.healthdataportal.eu/editor2/>

¹³ <https://www.healthinformationportal.eu/about/health-information-portal-api>

¹⁴ <https://healthdataeu.pages.code.europa.eu/healthdcat-ap/releases/release-5/>

¹⁵ <https://www.healthinformationportal.eu/healthdcat-ap>

¹⁶ <https://www.phiri.eu/>

¹⁷ <https://www.inf-act.eu/>

¹⁸ <https://semiceu.github.io/DCAT-AP/releases/3.0.0/>

health-specific extensions. The output is a **Resource Description Framework (RDF) metadata record (DCAT)** that can be hosted in the portal's sandbox catalogue.^{19,20} The Health Information Portal essentially acts as a metadata registry for health datasets, so researchers can find data without the data itself being openly posted.

Table 1. Characteristic summary of the European Health Information Portal.

Characteristic	Description
Discovery interface	https://www.healthinformationportal.eu/services/find-data
Example	https://www.healthinformationportal.eu/health-information-sources/cancer-network-information-system
Governance	Developed by PHIRI ²¹ and InfAct; ²² hosted by Sciensano. ²³
Target scope	Population health and healthcare datasets; only metadata (no data transfer).
Main metadata standard(s)	HealthDCAT-AP (Draft under discussion, 22 Dec 2023) ^{24,25} aligned with DCAT-AP v3.0; Schema.org ; ²⁶ Data Documentation Initiative (DDI). ²⁷
Programmatic access	Yes, through a Fair Data Point (FDP) instance and Swagger. ²⁸
Cost	Free. The Health Information Portal is an EU-funded public service (no charge to create or host metadata records). There are no usage fees; data holders need only invest time to input their metadata.
Limitations	The catalogue is relatively new (~345 data sources as of December 2025); unclear sustainability (i.e., main projects within which it was developed ended in 2022 and 2023).

¹⁹ <https://www.healthinformationportal.eu/services/find-data>

²⁰ <https://ehds.healthdataportal.eu/index.py>

²¹ <https://www.phiri.eu/>

²² <https://www.inf-act.eu/>

²³ <https://www.sciensano.be/en>

²⁴ <https://metadata.healthdataportal.eu/dev.py?N=66&O=2731>

²⁵ <https://www.healthinformationportal.eu/healthdcat-ap>

²⁶ <https://schema.org/>

²⁷ <https://ddialliance.org/>

²⁸ <https://www.healthinformationportal.eu/about/health-information-portal-api>

3.1.2. Submission requirements

We assume that the *Dataset Access Rights* for the datasets to be submitted is 'Sensitive Data'. This field, which takes the values of 'Open Data', 'Protected Data' and 'Sensitive Data', changes submission requirements in the editor.²⁹

See details of metadata requirements at [Table 2](#).

Table 2. Metadata submission requirements for the European Health Information Portal.

Entity	Property
Technical Metadata	Dataset Identifier
Technical Metadata	Metadata Revision Date
Dataset	Title
Dataset	Description
Dataset	Keywords
Dataset	Provenance
Dataset	Purpose
Dataset	Geographical Coverage
Data access	Distribution
Data access	Sample (A sample distribution of the dataset)
Contacts	Publisher
Contacts	HDAB (Health Data Access Body)
Contacts	Contact Point(s)
Categorisation	Theme
Categorisation	Applicable Legislation
Categorisation	Health Category
Categorisation	Health Theme
Categorisation	Dataset Type

²⁹ <https://ehds.healthdataportal.eu/editor2/>

3.1.3. Submission process

Users must **register as a contributor** on the portal ³⁰ and then request **contributor credentials** for the metadata sandbox via EHDS2@sciensano.be. The process uses the HealthDCAT-AP Editor ³¹ to **fill in metadata fields** through the user-friendly UI (no programming expertise needed). The editor highlights mandatory and optional fields and even supports multi-language entries.

Once the record is complete and validated against the HealthDCAT-AP schema, the user can **publish it to the portal's sandbox catalogue**. To do so, one must contact the portal admins (EHDS2@sciensano.be) to get **publishing credentials**. After approval, the metadata is publicly accessible and shareable via the portal's "Find Data" catalogue interface. The portal also offers an API for metadata retrieval and a SHACL validator for DCAT-AP records.

Once the dataset record is in the sandbox catalogue, it can be registered further to be added to the official HIP catalogue. This process requires bespoke interaction with the portal maintainers.

3.2. IHCC Global Cohort Atlas

3.2.1. Overview

The **International Health Cohorts Consortium (IHCC)** ³² operates a Global Cohort Atlas: a **curated, open directory of large, longitudinal population cohorts** [2]. It lets researchers discover cohorts and cross-query cohort data dictionaries (variables, phenotypes, data types, policies), improving findability without exposing individual-level data. Atlas **metadata** (cohort descriptors, data dictionaries, variables) **are openly available** and versioned on GitHub, ^{33,34} enabling programmatic reuse. IHCC membership prioritizes very large cohorts but allows affiliate routes for smaller or under-represented populations.

Table 3. Characteristic summary of the IHCC Global Cohort Atlas.

Characteristic	Description
Discovery interface	https://atlas.ihccglobal.org
Example	https://www.ntnu.edu/hunt *
Governance	Developed as a collaboration between the Global Genomic

³⁰ <https://www.healthinformationportal.eu/register>

³¹ <https://ehds.healthdataportal.eu/editor2/>

³² <https://atlas.ihccglobal.org/>

³³ <https://registry.ihccglobal.app/ontologies/gecko>

³⁴ <https://github.com/IHCC-cohorts>

Characteristic	Description
	Medicine Collaborative (G2MC) ³⁵ and the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH); ³⁶
Target scope	Large longitudinal population cohorts (not disease-specific), with biospecimens and willingness to share data/metadata. Affiliate routes exist for special/under-represented groups. Only metadata (no data transfer).
Main metadata standard(s)	Cohort descriptors and data dictionaries with semantic harmonisation (Levels L1-L3). Built on/aligned with Maelstrom [3] and GA4GH frameworks [4]; uses GECKO ontology for cohort/variable description. ³⁷
Programmatic access	Yes, all public cohort metadata (descriptors, data dictionaries, variables) downloadable from IHCC GitHub; suitable for scripted harvest; also an API in development. ³⁸
Cost	Free to be indexed; curation/membership has no fee.
Limitations	Curated membership (not a general dataset portal). Variable-level coverage varies by cohort harmonisation level (levels 1-3); Atlas catalogs cohorts/variables, not individual records. IHCC originated as a funded initiative, but now public information focuses on its cohort atlas and scientific activities, with the current funding status and development plans not clearly documented.

**Example result after filtering at the IHCC portal with Healthcare Information = "Hospitalizations"; Lifestyle And Behaviours = "Alcohol use history"; Medication = "Administration"; Perception of Health and Quality of Life = "Functional limitations".*

3.2.2. Submission requirements

IHCC uses a three-level curation: Level 1 (high-level cohort fields upon joining), Level 2 (structured cohort descriptors via surveys), Level 3 (complete semantic harmonisation of the data dictionary variables).

Submission requirements are unclear in public-facing documentation, and contact details of maintainers (ihccinfo@ihccglobal.org) seem to be outdated or not monitored. Alternatives like EMBL-EBI's Cohort Atlas³⁹ are better maintained but are still in development.

³⁵ <https://www.nationalacademies.org/our-work/global-genomic-medicine-collaborative-g2mc>

³⁶ <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

³⁷ <https://github.com/IHCC-cohorts/GECKO>

³⁸ <https://github.com/IHCC-cohorts/ihcc-api>

³⁹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/cohortatlas/>

3.2.3. Submission process

To contribute a cohort, contributors first confirm eligibility, ensuring their cohort is large (typically >100,000 participants), longitudinal, population-based (non-disease specific), with biospecimens and willingness to share metadata. Then, contributors contact IHCC via ihccinfo@ihccglobal.org to begin membership.

Once accepted, they complete a Level 1 survey gathering high-level cohort descriptors to be included in the Atlas. Over time, cohorts may enrich their entry by providing structured descriptors (Level 2) via annual surveys and ultimately submit a fully harmonized data dictionary (Level 3) annotated against IHCC's semantic standards (e.g. GECKO ontology), with support from IHCC's harmonisation team. The result is open metadata published via the Atlas and its GitHub repository.

3.3. GraphDB

3.3.1. Overview

Ontotext's **GraphDB** is a high-performance **RDF triplestore and knowledge-graph database** supporting SPARQL, W3C semantics (RDF/OWL), and real-time inference.

This platform enables building large-scale, semantic metadata integration systems. It is ideal for federating dataset metadata across diverse sources without centralizing data. Briefly, GraphDB handles billions of triples, integrates with search engines (Lucene/Solr/Elasticsearch), enables advanced reasoning (e.g., if `Alice` is an `rdf:type Person`, and `Person` is a subclass of `Mammal`, then `Alice` is an `rdf:type Mammal`), and supports graph-based enrichment workflows.

It is relevant to note that GraphDB is not intended to store large primary datasets (e.g., clinical images), although, by design, it can store any RDF data (both metadata and domain data).

Table 4. Characteristic summary of GraphDB.

Characteristic	Description
Discovery interface	None by default. It's a backend RDF triplestore.
Example	Free sandbox demo ⁴⁰ available upon registration.
Governance	Developed and maintained by Ontotext (merged with Semantic Web Company into Graphwise in 2024), ⁴¹ a commercial semantic technology vendor.

⁴⁰ <https://sandbox.graphwise.ai/demos>

⁴¹

<https://www.ontotext.com/company/news/semantic-web-company-and-ontotext-merge-to-create-knowledge-graph-and-ai-powerhouse-graphwise/>

Characteristic	Description
Target scope	Broad and flexible RDF-based metadata integration. For example, datasets, variables, sample-level, ontologies, etc. Only metadata (no data transfer).
Main metadata standard(s)	Fully compliant with W3C RDF (v1.1), OWL, SPARQL (v1.1) standards; supports ontology reasoning (OWL 2 RL, RDFS).
Programmatic access	Yes. Supports SPARQL endpoints, ⁴² REST APIs, ⁴³ plus connectors for Lucene, Solr, Elasticsearch. ⁴⁴
Cost	There is a free edition (<i>GraphDB Free</i>) and a commercial edition (<i>GraphDB Enterprise</i>). Limitations (e.g., single core) apply to the free tier. ⁴⁵
Limitations	GraphDB is an internal backend platform for ingesting and managing RDF metadata: it's not a public discovery portal <i>per se</i> . To make it a dataset discovery tool for external researchers, HEREDITARY may need to build a frontend interface (e.g., https://hereditary-project.eu/metadata , GUI, or search UI) on top of GraphDB built-in SPARQL endpoint.

3.3.2. Submission requirements

GraphDB does **not impose domain-specific submission requirements** for metadata. Instead, it provides a technical infrastructure where any RDF data can be uploaded by users.

Submission to GraphDB means "ingesting data into a triplestore" via its interface; there are no mandatory metadata schema checks at entry.

Supported RDF formats include `.ttl`, `.ttls`, `.rdf`, `.rdfs`, `.xml`, `.n3`, `.nt`, `.nq`, `.trig`, `.trigs`, `.trix`, `.owl`, `.brf`, `.jsonld`, `.ndjsonld`, `.jsonl`, `.ndjson`, `.rj`.⁴⁶

⁴² <https://graphdb.ontotext.com/documentation/11.0/sparql-compliance.html>

⁴³ <https://graphdb.ontotext.com/documentation/11.0/manage-repos-with-restapi.html>

⁴⁴

<https://graphdb.ontotext.com/documentation/11.0/full-text-search.html#full-text-search-using-the-graphdb-connectors>

⁴⁵

https://www.ontotext.com/products/graphdb/?_gl=1*v8g2c2*_ga*Mjc5NTQ0NjU3LjE3NDY3MjMjM.*_ga_HGSKWBWCRK*czE3NTczMzI3NDkzbzZkZkdDE3NTczMzM5NjYkajI0JGwwJGgw#comparison-table

⁴⁶ <https://graphdb.ontotext.com/documentation/11.1/rdf-formats.html>

3.3.3. Submission process

Users provide their metadata in RDF formats (e.g., Turtle) and load it into GraphDB using its tools: the Workbench UI, ⁴⁷ the SPARQL/RDF4J API, ⁴⁸ or ImportRDF ⁴⁹ tool for large datasets.

No specific schema or content validation is enforced, as GraphDB focuses on the technical import and management of RDF data. Once loaded, the data resides in a GraphDB repository, ready for query, inference, or further enrichment.

3.4. European Genome–Phenome Archive

3.4.1. Overview

The **European Genome–Phenome Archive** (EGA), jointly managed by EMBL-EBI and the Centre for Genomic Regulation (CRG), is a **secure, controlled-access repository for human genomic and phenotypic data** consented for biomedical research [5]. It's part of the ELIXIR Core Data Resources and designed to archive and share potentially identifiable genetic and clinical data, while strictly enforcing consent and ethical permissions. ⁵⁰

It provides persistent identifiers and structured metadata for multiple entities (e.g., datasets, samples, experiments...), enhancing **dataset findability** while safeguarding privacy.

Furthermore, it has evolved into a federated network of EGA nodes: the **Federated EGA** [6]. This system is the **primary global resource for discovery and access of sensitive human omics** and associated data consented for secondary use. It relies on a network of national human data repositories to accelerate disease research and improve human health.

Metadata-only submissions are possible but not advisable: commonly, **submissions to the EGA include the data** (e.g., sequencing files, Electronic Health Records...) as well. This information can be either submitted to EGA or, in case of existing data transfer restrictions, it can be submitted to a local FEGA node. For example, if a dataset from UNIPD has its policy restricting the data not to leave its country of origin, it could be submitted to the Italian FEGA node.

Table 5. Characteristic summary of the EGA.

Characteristic	Description
Discovery interface	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Datasets: https://ega-archive.org/datasets/ • Studies: https://ega-archive.org/studies/

⁴⁷ <https://graphdb.ontotext.com/documentation/11.1/working-with-workbench.html>

⁴⁸ <https://graphdb.ontotext.com/documentation/11.1/rdf4j-rest-api.html>

⁴⁹ <https://graphdb.ontotext.com/documentation/11.1/loading-data-using-importrdf.html>

⁵⁰ <https://ega-archive.org/about/ega/>

Characteristic	Description
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Access Committees (DAC): https://ega-archive.org/dacs/
Example	https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD00001011131
Governance	Operated by EMBL-EBI and CRG. ⁵¹
Target scope	Human genomic and phenotypic datasets requiring controlled access.
Main metadata standard(s)	Metadata schema is a derivation of the INSDC-compliant European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) model. ⁵² EGA is a driver project of GA4GH (e.g., DUO codes, Phenopackets...) products [5].
Programmatic access	Yes, both submission (WEBIN API ⁵³ and Submitter API) ⁵⁴ and discovery (Metadata API ⁵⁵ and future Beacon-v2 instance). ⁵⁶
Cost	Free. No charges to deposit or access metadata.
Limitations	Commonly, submissions contain both the metadata and data. Given the sensitivity of the archival, (1) submission can be time-consuming, potentially requiring several weeks from initial registration to approved ingestion; and (2) metadata is partly public but identifiable details are restricted.

3.4.2. Submission requirements

See details of metadata requirements at [Table 6](#).

Table 6. Metadata submission requirements for the EGA.

Entity	Property
Analysis	Description
Analysis	Files
Analysis	Title
Analysis	Type

⁵¹ <https://ega-archive.org/about/ega/>

⁵² <https://ega-archive.org/submission/metadata/ega-schema/>

⁵³ <https://ega-archive.org/submission/metadata/submission/programmatic-submission-xml/>

⁵⁴

<https://ega-archive.org/submission/metadata/submission/sequencing-phenotype/submitter-portals-api/>

⁵⁵ <https://ega-archive.org/discovery/metadata/public-metadata-api/>

⁵⁶ <https://ega-archive.org/about/projects-and-funders/beacon/>

Entity	Property
DAC	Title
Dataset	Description
Dataset	Title
Dataset	Type
Experiment	Design Name
Experiment	Library layout
Experiment	Library selection type
Experiment	Library source type
Experiment	Library strategy type
Experiment	Model (of platform)
Experiment	Platform
Policy	Policy content
Policy	Title
Policy	URL (policy content)
Run	Files
Run	Format
Sample	Alias
Sample	Biological sex
Sample	Phenotype
Sample	Subject ID (<i>free text</i>)
Study	Description
Study	Study type
Study	Title

3.4.3. Submission process

First, researchers register for an EGA account, request a Submitter role, and sign a Data Processing Agreement (DPA) validated by the helpdesk.

Once accredited, data files are encrypted and uploaded via secure channels into an assigned submission inbox. Metadata must then be registered either programmatically or through the Submitter Portal (SP).

After linking uploaded files with metadata objects and finalizing the submission, the EGA Helpdesk reviews and approves the entry. Upon approval, non-identifiable metadata becomes publicly visible in the EGA catalog, while data access remains governed by the DAC.

3.5. BioStudies

3.5.1. Overview

EMBL-EBI **BioStudies** is a flexible and inclusive **repository for study-level metadata in the life sciences** [7]. It aggregates all data outputs associated with a study, including links to structured domain-specific archives (e.g., ENA, ⁵⁷ ArrayExpress), ⁵⁸ external repositories, and supplementary files that lack dedicated archives.

BioStudies supports **multimodal datasets** and makes them discoverable via a single study record. It enables a coherent and citable record for each study. BioStudies also supports versioning, integrates with manuscript workflows (e.g., via Europe PMC), ⁵⁹ and enhances reproducibility and the citation of data across diverse research outputs.

Table 7. Characteristic summary of BioStudies.

Characteristic	Description
Discovery interface	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/studies/
Example	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/europepmc/studies/S-EPMC11253007
Governance	Developed and maintained by EMBL-EBI. ⁶⁰
Target scope	Life sciences studies of all kinds, particularly multimodal, supplementary, or <i>orphan</i> datasets not captured in specialized archives; study-level metadata plus optional hosting of associated non-sensitive files (not suitable for sensitive personal data).

⁵⁷ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>

⁵⁸ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/arrayexpress>

⁵⁹ <https://europepmc.org/>

⁶⁰ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/>

Characteristic	Description
Main metadata standard(s)	Compliant with MAGE-TAB ⁶¹ and MINSEQE; ⁶² integrates services like DOIs, ⁶³ and ontologies such as EFO. ⁶⁴
Programmatic access	Supports API endpoints, FTP/Aspera for file retrieval, and indexing in Europe PMC and EMBL-EBI's search platforms.
Cost	Free to submit and access.
Limitations	Does not support granular, structured variable-level metadata searches; acts as a catch-all metadata envelope.

3.5.2. Submission requirements

See details of metadata requirements at [Table 8](#).

Table 8. Metadata submission requirements for BioStudies.

Entity	Property
Study	Title
Study	Release Date
Study	Description
Study	Organism
Contact	Name
Contact	Email
Contact	Organisation

3.5.3. Submission process

Authors or project teams begin by registering or logging into the BioStudies submission portal. ⁶⁵ They then create a study-level record by filling out metadata fields and attaching supplementary files. Additionally, one can add URIs pointing to data hosted elsewhere (structured archives or general-purpose repositories). ⁶⁶

⁶¹ <https://fairsharing.org/1254>

⁶² <https://fairsharing.org/1206>

⁶³ <https://fairsharing.org/1332>

⁶⁴ <https://fairsharing.org/1498>

⁶⁵ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/submissions/signin>

⁶⁶ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/submit>

For functional genomics data, Annotare ⁶⁷ can facilitate structured metadata submission in MAGE-TAB format, enabling downstream reuse. On submission, the record may receive an accession or DOI-like identifier and becomes discoverable via EMBL-EBI's search interfaces. If it is linked to a publication, it also surfaces in Europe PMC records. ⁶⁸ When necessary, datasets can remain private (e.g., during review), as BioStudies supports versioning and conditional release.

3.6. Beacon v2

3.6.1. Overview

Beacon v2 ⁶⁹ is an officially GA4GH-approved standard (April 2022) for **federated discovery of genomic and phenotypic data**, designed for complex, ontology-rich queries and tiered access across sensitive human data systems [8].

It replaces Beacon v1 by supporting **queries across multiple entities** (including variants, individuals, biosamples and cohorts/datasets) with RESTful APIs, filters via ontologies (CURIEs), rich response modes (e.g., boolean, counts, record handover), and secure AAI (Passports, DUO codes) integration.

Beacon v2 is becoming increasingly adopted in ELIXIR Europe and clinical genomics networks, and is considered a *lingua franca* for federated data discovery.

Table 9. Characteristic summary of Beacon v2.

Characteristic	Description
Discovery interface	REST API (Beacon Framework + Model); no visual interface for discovery.
Example	https://beaconplus.progenetix.org
Governance	Developed by GA4GH Discovery Work Stream; ⁷⁰ implemented by different services locally.
Target scope	Federation of genomic and phenotypic datasets across sensitive data environments; only metadata (no data transfer).
Main metadata standard(s)	Beacon model ⁷¹ was heavily influenced by Phenopackets.
Programmatic access	Yes, JSON over REST.

⁶⁷ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/fg/annotare/help/index.html>

⁶⁸ <https://europepmc.org/>

⁶⁹ <https://genomebeacons.org/>

⁷⁰ https://www.ga4gh.org/work_stream/discovery/

⁷¹ <https://github.com/ga4gh-beacon/beacon-v2/tree/main/models/json/beacon-v2-default-model>

Characteristic	Description
Cost	Open-source (most components with explicit Apache-2.0/GPL v3 licenses).
Limitations	Requires local deployment and "beaconization" of metadata; not a standalone portal; visibility relies on federated networks adhering to the framework.

3.6.2. Submission requirements

Requirements for deployment aside (see [submission process](#) for details), [Table 10](#) summarises the metadata that would be required if HEREDITARY datasets were to be added to a Beacon network.

Since the framework is flexible in what can be added and displayed (e.g., datasets with genomic variants or without them), the following requirements assume a minimal informative submission of Dataset,⁷² Individual,⁷³ BioSample,⁷⁴ Cohort,⁷⁵ Genomic variations⁷⁶ and Analyses⁷⁷ / Runs.⁷⁸

Table 10. Metadata submission requirements for Beacon-v2.

Entity	Property
Datasets	name
Individuals	sex
Biosamples	biosampleStatus
Biosamples	sampleOriginType
GenomicVariations	alternateBases
GenomicVariations	location (e.g., interval, sequence_id...)
GenomicVariations	variantType
Analyses	pipelineName
Analyses	analysisDate

⁷² https://docs.genomebeacons.org/schemas-md/datasets_defaultSchema/#__tabbed_1_2

⁷³ https://docs.genomebeacons.org/schemas-md/individuals_defaultSchema/#__tabbed_1_1

⁷⁴ https://docs.genomebeacons.org/schemas-md/biosamples_defaultSchema/#__tabbed_1_1

⁷⁵ https://docs.genomebeacons.org/schemas-md/cohorts_defaultSchema/#__tabbed_1_1

⁷⁶

https://docs.genomebeacons.org/schemas-md/genomicVariations_defaultSchema/#__tabbed_1_1

⁷⁷ https://docs.genomebeacons.org/schemas-md/analyses_defaultSchema/#__tabbed_1_1

⁷⁸ https://docs.genomebeacons.org/schemas-md/runs_defaultSchema/#__tabbed_1_1

Entity	Property
Runs	runDate
Runs	biosampleId
Cohorts	cohortType
Cohorts	name

3.6.3. Submission process

Submission to a Beacon-v2 network can be understood as the addition of new records (e.g., Dataset) to an existing or new Beacon-v2 implementation. Therefore, the process highly depends on the existing setting. For example, HEREDITARY datasets may be beaconised as part of another beacon (e.g., EGA) or have a new beacon entirely developed for the project.

If the latter, it involves preparing metadata in the Beacon data model (i.e., creating JSON structures for datasets, cohorts, variants...), loading the metadata into an implementation (e.g., B2RI), configuring access policies (e.g., anonymous, registered, controlled) and AAI integration. Finally, it would involve testing for compliance.

Once deployed, the endpoint can serve queries and can be registered in federated networks like ELIXIR Beacon Network or 1+MG/GDI for broader discoverability.

3.7. Molgenis

3.7.1. Overview

Molgenis, derived from 'molecular genetics information system', is an open-source, modular **data platform for molecular genetics research** [9]. It is widely used across domains such as biobanking, patient registries, rare disease research, and data catalogues.

Molgenis supports building **customisable data management systems**, allowing users to model, collect, manage, analyse, visualise, and share scientific data via a web interface. Therefore, it is **not a catalogue itself**, but rather a software platform (i.e., back-end infrastructure) **used to build catalogues** (e.g., European health data and sample network catalogue),⁷⁹ among other features.⁸⁰

Molgenis is ELIXIR-recommended for interoperability.⁸¹

⁷⁹ <https://molgeniscatalogue.org/>

⁸⁰ <https://molgenis.org/communities.html>

⁸¹ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/interoperability/rirs>

Table 11. Characteristic summary of Molgenis.

Characteristic	Description
Discovery interface	Configurable, and locally hosted, UI exposing data catalogues/search tools.
Example	https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/ERIC/directory/#/catalogue
Governance	Developed and maintained by UMCG's Genomics Coordination Center (GCC).
Target scope	Scientific datasets across biobanking, clinical research, registries, rare diseases, multi-omics. Flexible and domain-agnostic. ⁸²
Main metadata standard(s)	Fully customizable backend metadata schema enables each instance to follow different standards (e.g., MIABIS). ⁸³
Programmatic access	Yes, via REST APIs (Data API, Metadata API, Beacon API, FAIR API), Swagger, Python client. ⁸⁴
Cost	Free (if locally hosted) and open-source under LGPL v3. ⁸⁵ Fees apply for GCC hosted service. ⁸⁶
Limitations	Molgenis is only a platform infrastructure; deployment, hosting, and metadata modelling require effort and maintenance from the deployers; it is not a public portal in itself, but can be used to build one.

3.7.2. Submission requirements

Molgenis is a self-hosted software framework, not a central portal. Therefore, it imposes **no mandatory content submission requirements**. Instead, requirements reflect self-defined configuration.

3.7.3. Submission process

In order to make use of Molgenis in HEREDITARY, a hosting service would be required: either self-hosted or using the hosted service from GCC.⁸⁷ In summary, given the flexibility of the framework, one would need to set up a server, install and configure MOLGENIS, load the metadata from HEREDITARY and share it. This last part is also incredibly diverse, as some catalogues use (locally developed) UIs, while others use the programmatic access.

⁸² https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/molgenis_assembly#what-is-the-molgenis-tool-assembly

⁸³ <https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/howtomiabis/>

⁸⁴ <https://molgenis.gitbook.io/molgenis/interoperability>

⁸⁵ <https://molgenis.org/LICENSE-LGPLv3.html>

⁸⁶ <https://molgenis.org/learn.html>

⁸⁷ https://molgenis.org/attachments/MOLGENIS_DVO_annex4_20201120.pdf

3.8. BBMRI-ERIC Directory

3.8.1. Overview

The **BBMRI-ERIC Directory** is a central, Europe-wide catalogue of biobanks and their collections (samples and associated data) across BBMRI-ERIC member states [10].

It enables researchers to discover biobanks by country, sample types, quality labels, ICD-10 codes, and more. All of this without centralising any datasets: National Nodes curate and manage metadata submissions at the country level.

The Directory uses the MIABIS 2.0 Core model for metadata, supports a REST API for programmatic access, and is linked to downstream tools like the Negotiator [11], Locator⁸⁸ and Finder⁸⁹ for searching and requesting access to samples or data. It is also an implementation example of the [Molgenis platform](#).

As of September 2025, approximately 700 biobanks, from over 400 organisations, with over 3500 collections and 100+ million samples are aggregated in the BBMRI-ERIC Directory.⁹⁰

Table 12. Characteristic summary of the BBMRI-ERIC Directory.

Characteristic	Description
Discovery interface	https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu
Example	https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/ERIC/directory/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB20-017
Governance	Developed and hosted by BBMRI-ERIC's Common Service IT team; centrally managed from Graz, Austria, and coordinated via National Nodes across participating Member States. ⁹¹
Target scope	Aggregated metadata about biobanks, collections of human biosamples and associated metadata; only metadata (no data transfer).
Main metadata standard(s)	MIABIS 2.0 Core (Minimum Information About Biobank-sample) [12].
Programmatic access	Yes. REST API available for Directory; downstream tools (Locator, Finder, Negotiator) are integrated programmatically too.
Cost	Free for member and observer countries' biobanks to be listed (metadata management by National Nodes); no fees mentioned.

⁸⁸ <https://locator.bbmri-eric.eu/>

⁸⁹ <https://finder.bbmri-eric.eu/>

⁹⁰ <https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/ERIC/directory/#/catalogue>

⁹¹ <https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/governance-structure/>

Characteristic	Description
Limitations	Requires National Node mediation; metadata is structured only per defined model; scope does not include high-level datasets.

3.8.2. Submission requirements

To be included in the BBMRI-ERIC Directory, a biobank must submit aggregated metadata according to standards curated by its National Node. The minimal denominators findable in the federated platform tools are listed in [Table 13](#).

Table 13. Metadata submission requirements for the Federated Platform tools of BBMRI-ERIC.

Entity	Property
Individual	Date of diagnosis
Individual	Diagnosis
Individual	Donor age at diagnosis (years)
Individual	Donor age (years)
Individual	Sex
Sample	Sampling date
Sample	Sample type
Sample	Storage temperature

3.8.3. Submission process

If HEREDITARY were to participate, metadata would be submitted via the respective National Nodes, which operate a staging area where data is curated and harmonised.⁹²

National Nodes may enter metadata manually, upload Excel/CSV files, or use scheduled ingest or the REST API. After staging and verification, metadata is synchronized nightly into the central BBMRI-ERIC Directory, where it becomes discoverable.

⁹²

https://www.ejprarediseases.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/EJPRD_P2_D11.11_PU_First-ver_Addition-Facilities-Integrated-Resources_Data-Deposit-Access_FV.pdf

3.9. BioSamples

3.9.1. Overview

The EMBL-EBI BioSamples database is a central hub for sample-level metadata across life sciences. It assigns stable accessions (e.g. SAMEA...) and links samples to downstream assay resources such as the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA),⁹³ ArrayExpress,⁹⁴ Proteomics Identifications Database (PRIDE),⁹⁵ MetaboLights⁹⁶ and others, improving cross-archive findability without holding raw data [13].

Table 14. Characteristic summary of BioSamples.

Characteristic	Description
Discovery interface	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples
Example	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/samples/SAMN44593789
Governance	Developed and maintained by EMBL-EBI. ⁹⁷
Target scope	Sample metadata (human and non-human); only metadata (no data transfer).
Main metadata standard(s)	JSON Schema is used to validate samples against pre-defined checklists based on the type of sample. ⁹⁸
Programmatic access	REST API for submit/update/validate; ⁹⁹ supports programmatic searches with external references and relationships. ¹⁰⁰
Cost	Free to submit and access metadata.
Limitations	Stores sample-level metadata (not full dataset catalogues); metadata should not be personally identifiable.

3.9.2. Submission requirements

Minimal metadata requirements are encoded in the BioSamples Minimal checklist,¹⁰¹ also shown in [Table 15](#).

⁹³ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>

⁹⁴ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/arrayexpress>

⁹⁵ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pride/>

⁹⁶ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>

⁹⁷ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/about>

⁹⁸ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/docs/guides/validation>

⁹⁹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/submit>

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/docs/references/api/search>

¹⁰¹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/schemas/certification/biosamples-minimal.json>

Table 15. Metadata submission requirements for BioSamples.

Entity	Property
Sample	name
Sample	Organism (e.g., 9606 for humans)

3.9.3. Submission process

Submitting to BioSamples is straightforward: (1) a user in HEREDITARY creates an account; (2) submits metadata either through the UI or JSON API; (3) records are archived, accessioned and released. From that moment on, the record can be referenced somewhere else (e.g., BioStudies).

3.10. Zenodo

3.10.1. Overview

Zenodo is a free, general-purpose research repository operated by CERN with OpenAIRE since 2013.¹⁰² The platform itself is open-source and actively maintained at Zenodo's GitHub repository.¹⁰³

It issues **DOIs** via DataCite, preserves all research outputs (data, software, publications, etc.), exposes metadata for harvesting (OAI-PMH), and provides a REST Deposition API. The main incentives of Zenodo are the **citability** of its records, **versioning**, and document **indexing**.

Submitted metadata fall under CC0 licence. Sensitive/personal data are not suitable for Zenodo. The platform imposes relatively few constraints. For example, file and record limits, and requires depositors to choose a licence and comply with content policies.

Although metadata-only records are not supported (each record must include at least one file), submissions of datasets with their dataset summaries and policies as documents would be suitable. Access to files can be restricted/closed, commonly to allow for artefacts to be created and reviewed while research is still ongoing.

Default size limits are 50 GB per record and per file (up to 100 files),¹⁰⁴ with possible one-off increases. A public sandbox exists for testing.

¹⁰² <https://doi.org/10.25495/7gxx-rd71>

¹⁰³ <https://github.com/zenodo/zenodo-rdm>

¹⁰⁴ <https://help.zenodo.org/docs/deposit/manage-files/#prepare>

Table 16. Characteristic summary of Zenodo.

Characteristic	Description
Discovery interface	https://zenodo.org/search
Example	Any of the 60+ submissions from HEREDITARY. ¹⁰⁵ For example, the dataset https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16919945 .
Governance	Operated by CERN; built within OpenAIRE. ¹⁰⁶
Target scope	General-purpose repository for research outputs (datasets, software, publications); not suitable for sensitive personal data , only aggregated non-identifiable data.
Main metadata standard(s)	DataCite (DOIs/metadata); ¹⁰⁷ OAI-PMH for harvesting; ¹⁰⁸ vocabularies for access rights from Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR). ^{109,110}
Programmatic access	Yes. Programmatic deposition through REST API; ¹¹¹ Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH). ¹¹²
Cost	Free to use. The only fees are for one-off quota increases beyond the default file size/number limits. ¹¹³
Limitations	Not suitable for identifiable sensitive data.

3.10.2. Submission requirements

As mentioned above, each submission is required to contain at least one file. This limitation is unlikely to affect HEREDITARY datasets, as they could go along dataset descriptions or their policies.

Furthermore, metadata requirements are listed at [Table 17](#).

Table 17. Metadata submission requirements for Zenodo.

Entity	Property
Record	Resource type

¹⁰⁵ <https://zenodo.org/communities/hereditaryproject/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10>

¹⁰⁶ <https://about.zenodo.org/>

¹⁰⁷ <https://datacite.org/>

¹⁰⁸ <https://developers.zenodo.org/#oai-pmh>

¹⁰⁹ <https://about.zenodo.org/principles>

¹¹⁰ https://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org/access_rights/

¹¹¹ <https://developers.zenodo.org/?python#rest-api>

¹¹² <https://zenodo.org/oai2d>

¹¹³ <https://help.zenodo.org/docs/deposit/manage-files/quota-increase/>

Entity	Property
Record	Title
Record	Publication date
Creators	Name
Access rights	Visibility

3.10.3. Submission process

A submitter simply needs to sign in at Zenodo (e.g., through ORCID/GitHub) and then open a new upload page. After attaching at least one file and filling in the metadata fields (see bare minimum at [Table 17](#)), the submitter clicks on "Publish".

It is worth noting that the HEREDITARY project already has an existing community "HEREDITARY Project" ¹¹⁴ that new submissions would need to belong to.

3.11. data.europa.eu (EU Open Data Portal)

3.11.1. Overview

The **data.europa.eu** service is the EU's official **metadata aggregator** for public sector data from EU institutions, agencies and Member States. It is the single point of access to open and geospatial data from national/regional portals and EU bodies, replacing the former EU Open Data Portal and European Data Portal. ¹¹⁵

It commonly does not host datasets, and instead it **harvests DCAT-AP metadata** from provider catalogues and exposes them for discovery, quality checks and reuse. There are exceptions in which data and metadata can be submitted. ¹¹⁶ The portal's core model is DCAT-AP 2.1.1, and it offers Metadata Quality Assessment (MQA) and guidance to improve records.

Table 18. Characteristic summary of data.europa.eu.

Characteristic	Description
Discovery interface	data.europa.eu
Example	https://data.europa.eu/data/datasets/https-doi-org-10-5878-ejpi-p674

¹¹⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/hereditaryproject/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10>

¹¹⁵ <https://dataeuropa.gitlab.io/data-provider-manual/>

¹¹⁶ <https://dataeuropa.gitlab.io/data-provider-manual/our-metadata-model/>

Characteristic	Description
Governance	Funded by the EU and managed operationally by the Publications Office of the European Union in cooperation with the Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology of the European Commission, responsible for EU open data policy. ¹¹⁷
Target scope	Aggregated metadata about public sector datasets across all EU institutions, agencies, and Member States; cross-domain (health, transport, environment, etc.); only metadata (no data transfer).
Main metadata standard(s)	DCAT-AP in the portal is version 2.1.1. ^{118,119}
Programmatic access	Yes, through SPARQL endpoint, ¹²⁰ DCAT-AP harvest, ¹²¹ REST API, ¹²² and bulk download.
Cost	Free. No charges to submit or access metadata.
Limitations	No health-specific extensions (unlike HIP). Relies on harvesting from existing catalogues; providers must operate a DCAT-AP or compatible API endpoint.

3.11.2. Submission requirements

To be harvestable by data.europa.eu, a provider must expose a DCAT-AP-compliant catalogue or supported API. ¹²³ Therefore, minimal submission requirements are those of DCAT-AP (v2.1.1). ¹²⁴

The minimal mandatory metadata requirements listed in [Table 19](#) are identical in DCAT-AP v2.1.1 and in v3.0.1 ¹²⁵ (the latest specification). We present them here following v3.0.1 URIs for improved documentation and alignment with the most up-to-date profiles, while ensuring compatibility with the current portal implementation.

Furthermore, controlled vocabularies for some of these terms are enforced in both v2.1.1 ¹²⁶ and v3.0.1. ¹²⁷

¹¹⁷ <https://dataeuropa.gitlab.io/data-provider-manual/>

¹¹⁸ <https://dataeuropa.gitlab.io/data-provider-manual/our-metadata-model/>

¹¹⁹ <https://github.com/SEMICeu/DCAT-AP/tree/master/releases/2.1.1#dcat-ap-211>

¹²⁰ <https://dataeuropa.gitlab.io/data-provider-manual/how-to-search/sparql/>

¹²¹ <https://dataeuropa.gitlab.io/data-provider-manual/how-to-publish/request-harvesting/>

¹²² <https://dataeuropa.gitlab.io/data-provider-manual/api-documentation/>

¹²³ <https://dataeuropa.gitlab.io/data-provider-manual/how-to-publish>

¹²⁴ <https://github.com/SEMICeu/DCAT-AP/tree/master/releases/2.1.1#dcat-ap-211>

¹²⁵ <https://semiceu.github.io/DCAT-AP/releases/3.0.1/#provider-requirements>

¹²⁶

https://github.com/SEMICeu/DCAT-AP/blob/master/releases/2.1.1/dcat-ap_2.1.1_shacl_mdr-vocabularies.shape.ttl

¹²⁷ <https://semiceu.github.io/DCAT-AP/releases/3.0.1/#controlled-vocabularies-to-be-used>

Table 19. Metadata submission requirements for data.europa.eu (DCAT-AP v2.1.1 & v3.0.1).

Entity	Property
Agent (organisations)	Name
Catalogue	Description
Catalogue	Publisher
Catalogue	Title
Catalogue Record	Modification date
Catalogue Record	Primary topic
Data Service*	Endpoint URL
Data Service*	Title
Dataset	Description
Dataset	Title
Distribution*	Access URL

*Metadata required only where entities exist. For example, if datafiles are available through any Distributions, metadata for Distribution is required.

3.11.3. Submission process

First, HEREDITARY proprietary data sources would need to expose (e.g., preferably through OAI-PMH)¹²⁸ the dataset catalogue in DCAT-AP (v3.0.1). The catalogue endpoint is then submitted through the data provider manual to request harvesting and, once validated, the portal schedules regular harvests.¹²⁹ Providers of these data sources could then monitor their records using the Metadata Quality Assessment (MQA) dashboard to improve completeness and compliance.¹³⁰

3.12. Maelstrom Catalogue

3.12.1. Overview

The **Maelstrom Research Catalogue**¹³¹ is an open, web-based platform that supports the findability of population-based cohort studies and their variables. It was developed

¹²⁸ <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>

¹²⁹ <https://dataeuropa.gitlab.io/data-provider-manual/how-to-publish/request-harvesting/>

¹³⁰

<https://dataeuropa.gitlab.io/data-provider-manual/metadata-quality/#metadata-quality-dashboard>

¹³¹ <https://www.maelstrom-research.org/page/catalogue>

to promote transparent documentation, harmonisation, co-analysis and dissemination of epidemiological and longitudinal research data.¹³²

The catalogue indexes rich metadata about studies, datasets, and variables (e.g., questionnaires, clinical measures, biospecimens), without centralising individual-level data. Its main goal is to enable **discoverability and semantic alignment** (i.e., harmonisation) across large-scale cohort and health studies. Ultimately this supports researchers in identifying comparable datasets.

Maelstrom does not exclusively offer cataloguing services, but also provides a repertoire of open-source tools¹³³ that interconnect with each other: (1) **Rmonise**, as the main harmonisation toolkit;¹³⁴ (2) **Mica**, as a website building software;¹³⁵ (3) **Opal**, to manage, harmonize, and integrate data;¹³⁶ and (4) **DataShield** as their solution for co-analyzing sensitive research data.¹³⁷ These tools are widely used (e.g., Maelstrom standards informed the GECKO minimal metadata model that underpins the [IHCC Cohort Browser](#))^{138,139} and maintained as a free public resource.

Table 20. Characteristic summary of Maelstrom Catalogue.

Characteristic	Description
Discovery interface	https://www.maelstrom-research.org/individual-search
Example	https://www.maelstrom-research.org/study/alspac
Governance	Developed and maintained by Maelstrom Research at McGill University (Montreal, Canada). ^{140,141}
Target scope	Epidemiological study metadata, primarily population-based cohort studies and longitudinal epidemiological studies. Only metadata (no data transfer unless desired through Opal), such as clinical and lifestyle variables.
Main metadata standard(s)	Maelstrom Variable Catalogue model. Multiple harmonisation initiatives available, enabling high flexibility. More restrictive if studies are to be added to the main Maelstrom's catalogue (as opposed to building HEREDITARY's). ¹⁴²

¹³² <https://www.maelstrom-research.org/page/background>

¹³³ <https://www.maelstrom-research.org/page/software>

¹³⁴ <https://maelstrom-research.github.io/Rmonize-documentation/index.html>

¹³⁵ <https://www.obiba.org/pages/products/mica/>

¹³⁶ <https://www.obiba.org/pages/products/opal/>

¹³⁷ <https://datashield.org/>

¹³⁸ <https://www.maelstrom-research.org/page/current-partnerships>

¹³⁹ <https://www.maelstrom-research.org/page/past-partnerships>

¹⁴⁰ <https://www.maelstrom-research.org/page/team>

¹⁴¹ <https://www.maelstrom-research.org/page/background>

¹⁴² <https://www.maelstrom-research.org/harmonization-studies?>

Characteristic	Description
Programmatic access	Yes. REST API endpoints documented (e.g., Mica) ¹⁴³ for study and variable level metadata enquiries.
Cost	Free. No charges to contribute with or discover metadata in the catalogue. Only fees revolve around a cost-recovery model for their support if required. ¹⁴⁴
Limitations	Focused on population cohorts; not intended as a generic dataset metadata registry. No explicit compliance with 1+MG Frameworks, GA4GH or EU-standards such as Health DCAT-AP.

3.12.2. Submission requirements

To be indexed, cohorts must provide a **study's data dictionary**. If joining an existing network in Maelstrom, catalogue maintainers take on the task of harmonising variables under the Maelstrom data dictionaries to comply with existing networks.

On the other hand, if the network is built bespoke for HEREDITARY using Maelstrom's open-source tools, requirements are defined *ad-hoc* by developers.

3.12.3. Submission process

Prospective contributors contact Maelstrom Research to initiate the process. Depending on whether contributions are to be added to an existing network or not, the **harmonisation of the data** is performed by the catalogue maintainers or data contributors themselves, respectively.¹⁴⁵

If added to the **existing Maelstrom's catalogue**, metadata is validated against the catalogue model, using Opal and Mica.¹⁴⁶ Once accepted, study and variable metadata are made publicly discoverable via the Maelstrom Catalogue portals and APIs.

Alternatively, if chosen to **create a bespoke implementation** of the catalogue, similar to CanPath's Access Portal,¹⁴⁷ submission involves the deployment of several Maelstrom components. Furthermore, the role of catalogue maintainer is acquired by the platform deployer.

¹⁴³ <https://micadoc.obiba.org/en/latest/python-user-guide/doc/search.html?>

¹⁴⁴ <https://www.maelstrom-research.org/page/metadata-catalogues>

¹⁴⁵ <https://www.maelstrom-research.org/page/faq>

¹⁴⁶ <https://www.maelstrom-research.org/page/software>

¹⁴⁷ <https://portal.canpath.ca/>

3.13. Linked Life Data Inventory

3.13.1. Overview

Ontotext's LinkedLifeData Inventory (LLDI)¹⁴⁸ is a curated Life Sciences and Healthcare Data Inventory that provides access to more than 200 public biomedical datasets and ontologies in RDF format. It is designed as an accelerator for building domain knowledge graphs, particularly in pharma, biotech and biomedical research.

The inventory covers multiple domains, including genomics, proteomics, metabolomics, molecular interactions and biological processes, pharmacology, clinical and medical information, as well as scientific publications and clinical trials.

LLDI is organised as a map of data domains and is accessed via the LinkedLifeData Catalog system, which allows users to search and filter datasets and inspect dataset dashboards describing content and relationships to other datasets. Once relevant datasets are identified, they are loaded into [GraphDB](#) repositories and accessed through GraphDB Workbench¹⁴⁹ to build use case specific knowledge graphs.

Table 21. Characteristic summary of the Linked Life Data Inventory.

Characteristic	Description
Discovery interface	LinkedLifeData Catalog system (free demo available on request).
Example	https://www.ontotext.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/Screenshot-560.png
Governance	Developed and maintained by Ontotext (merged with Semantic Web Company into Graphwise in 2024), ¹⁵⁰ a commercial semantic technology vendor.
Target scope	Curated inventory of 200+ public life sciences and healthcare datasets and ontologies in RDF, spanning genomics, proteomics, metabolomics, molecular interactions, pharmacology, clinical and medical information, and scientific publications and trials. Intended to support knowledge graph construction and enrichment of proprietary data with public biomedical sources.
Main metadata standard(s)	RDF-based representation of all datasets, using W3C standards (RDF, OWL, SPARQL) via GraphDB . Datasets are semantically harmonised and mapped to reference ontologies and terminologies such as UMLS, SNOMED, LOINC, ICD-9/10 and others.

¹⁴⁸ <https://www.ontotext.com/solutions/healthcare-and-life-sciences/linked-life-data-inventory/>

¹⁴⁹ <https://graphdb.ontotext.com/documentation/10.1/graphdb-workbench.html>

¹⁵⁰

<https://www.ontotext.com/company/news/semantic-web-company-and-ontotext-merge-to-create-knowledge-graph-and-ai-powerhouse-graphwise/>

Characteristic	Description
Programmatic access	Yes, through GraphDB in deployed environments.
Cost	Commercial subscription / service. Access is provided via demos and Data-as-a-Service (DaaS) / Knowledge-Graph-as-a-Service (KGaaS) offerings; no free public tier is documented.
Limitations	LLDI is a vendor-curated inventory of public datasets rather than an open, community self-service catalogue; public documentation does not describe a workflow for external data owners to publish their own datasets into the inventory; its focus is on integrating public biomedical datasets and ontologies and using them to enrich proprietary data within knowledge graph solutions, rather than acting as a general-purpose discovery portal for third-party project datasets. Access is tied to commercial engagements.

3.13.2. Submission requirements

Public documentation describes Ontotext's internal FAIRification and semantic harmonisation process for the datasets included in LLDI, but does not define a public metadata template or explicit submission requirements for third-party contributors. Each dataset in the inventory is represented by a documented RDF schema and detailed description of its serialisations and semantic mappings to reference ontologies and terminologies. Automated update procedures are used to keep datasets current and consistent with defined schemas.

The inventory is maintained by Ontotext itself: the company compiles, normalises and maps public datasets and ontologies into RDF, and maintains them as part of its Life Sciences and Healthcare Data Inventory, rather than expecting external parties to conform to a published submission schema.

3.13.3. Submission process

There is **no self-service submission interface** documented for external data owners to register or publish their own datasets directly into LLDI. Instead, the described process is that potential users request a demo or contact Ontotext, subscribe to datasets enrichment (DaaS), or engage Ontotext to build and maintain their knowledge graph (KGaaS) that combines the inventory with the client's proprietary data.

4. Comparison of services

In this section we take all the services listed in [section 3](#) and succinctly compare them from the perspective of HEREDITARY Task 3.6, rather than from a neutral standpoint. This comparison is formatted in [Table 22](#), which has the following columns:

- **Service.** Name of the portal, platform or solution.

- **Scope.** The scope of the (meta)data supported by the service. Values from: **General** (domain-agnostic, e.g., research outputs), **Health** (Healthcare or Clinical data), **Genomics** (e.g., sequencing outputs and metadata), **Biobank** (e.g., sample metadata registry), **Cohorts** (e.g., Population studies); **Framework** (e.g., software to implement).
- **Discovery.** Method(s) of discovery of the service. Values from: **Portal** (e.g., human UI), **API** (programmatic access – e.g., REST/SPARQL/SDK...), **FED** (Federated network discovery).
- **Data Transfer.** Whether the service supports raw data transfer and archival or not. Especially relevant for data sources that *can* move raw data to portals with established Discoverability and Accessibility methods.
- **Cost.** Whether the service is free to use or requires a commercial license (i.e., a fee).
- **Access Control.** Whether the service supports Access Control (AC)¹⁵¹ or not.
- **Project ranking.** Subjective ranking given by the author of this landscape for each service, taking into consideration the project requirements and scope of Task 3.6. Values from: **High**, **Medium**, **Low**. See further details at the [discussion](#).

Table 22. Summary of evaluated portals and solutions. Colour format to aid with the ranking (darker green – better suited for the T3.6 purpose).

Service	Scope	Discovery	Data Transfer	Cost	Access Control	Project ranking
European Health Information Portal	Health, Cohorts	Portal, API	No	Free	No	High
European Genome–phenome Archive	Genomic, Health	Portal, API	Yes	Free	Yes	High
BioStudies	General	Portal, API	No*	Free	No	High
Beacon v2	Genomic, Framework	API, FED	No	Free	Yes	High
data.europa.eu	General	Portal, API	No*	Free	No	High
Maelstrom	Health, Cohorts, Framework	Portal, API, FED	No****	Free	Yes	High
BBMRI-ERIC Directory	Biobank, Cohorts	Portal, API	No	Free	Yes	Low

¹⁵¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Access_control

Service	Scope	Discovery	Data Transfer	Cost	Access Control	Project ranking
Linked Life Data Inventory	Health, Framework, Genomics	Portal, API***	No	Fee	No	Low
IHCC Global Cohort Atlas	Cohorts	Portal	No	Free	No	Medium
GraphDB	General, Framework	API	No	Free & Fee	Yes	Medium
Molgenis	General, Framework	Portal, API	Yes	Free	Yes	Medium
BioSamples	Biobank	Portal, API	No	Free	No	Medium
Zenodo	General	Portal, API	No*	Free	Yes**	Medium

* Files can be uploaded, but it is intended for study-level files, not to host large sensitive or personally identifiable data files.

**Zenodo allows depositing files under open, embargoed, restricted, or closed access, but metadata is always public.

***LLDI's portal is not a public-facing discovery tool, but rather an enrichment method for proprietary datasets.

****Maelstrom's Opal software offers file hosting, but it is not provided as a service.

5. Discussion

Our goal in Task 3.6 of the HEREDITARY project is to raise the discoverability of project datasets while staying compatible with EU frameworks (GDPR, EHDS, DCAT-AP/HealthDCAT-AP) and GA4GH/1+MG practices, and to do it with the **least development overhead** by identifying synergies with existing resources. The landscape review and our project context point to a pragmatic mix rather than a single portal.

For datasets where **data transfer is possible**, the [European Genome-phenome Archive](#) (EGA) (and national FEGA nodes), remain the most cost-effective and FAIR-compliant route: object accessioning, a widely used metadata model, clear controlled-access governance through DACs, and public discovery both via a portal and APIs. Project data sources submitting to the EGA would get multiple FAIR benefits (persistent IDs, standard governance and APIs...) without most of the technical overhead downsides.

Beyond the discoverability and interoperability improvements by submitting to EGA, other benefits to highlight are:

- **Accessibility.** Instead of bespoke DTAs per institution and granted access request, EGA provides GDPR-compliant access workflows and distribution infrastructure via DACs.
- **Reusability.** EGA provides long-term archival with persistent accessioning and governed reuse.

When **raw data cannot leave host institutions**, non-sensitive dataset metadata shall be submitted to data.europa.eu. The easiest and cost-effective method to do so is through the [European Health Information Portal](#) (HIP), which provides a HealthDCAT-AP-aligned catalogue to submit metadata to. Creating dataset records through the [HealthDCAT-AP editor](#) and then submitting them to the HIP's sandbox enables the project to create rich metadata records without exposing sensitive data. Furthermore, because HIP natively conforms to DCAT, submitted dataset records are formatted for harvesting and reuse by EU aggregators like data.europa.eu. This highlights the HIP as an EU-compatible *front door* for metadata on sensitive datasets. It is relevant to note that, at the moment, dataset records submitted to HIP's sandbox catalogue **do not automatically get harvested by data.europa.eu or get published in the HIP**. It is foreseen that HIP will become the Human health catalogue of data.europa.eu, a role that is currently missing in the catalogue dashboard.¹⁵² For this reason, creating HealthDCAT-AP records of HEREDITARY datasets in the HIP sandbox catalogue provides project collaborators with a smooth transition towards EU-wide discoverability.

For multimodal studies and paper-linked outputs, [Zenodo](#) and [BioStudies](#) provide a **citable dataset- and study-level landing page** that links to domain archives (e.g., EGA) and external resources. To avoid duplicates with other submissions, we advocate for linking rather than re-hosting: use Zenodo/BioStudies to point to EGA accessions (for controlled data) and to HIP/data.europa.eu records (for discovery), keeping a single source of truth per entity.

The four services listed above have the following key denominators:

- Their **scopes** cover our study-, dataset- and access-levels required for high-level dataset discoverability.
- They are **free to use** for both submitters and end-users.
- They require **no additional development**: systems can be used straightaway and are hosted by their respective institutions.
- They provide a **web portal** for human search and an **API** for programmatic harvesting.

Beyond dataset-level metadata, [Beacon-v2](#) enables federated queries over **biosamples, individuals and variants**, while data remain local. Beacon-v2 is an open source GA4GH standard, albeit using it requires an implementation effort (i.e.,

¹⁵² <https://data.europa.eu/mqa/catalogues>

beaconisation) by the project data sources. This effort is already being undertaken by Task 3.4 of the project and will go hand-in-hand with Task 3.6 proposals.

The **existing [Maelstrom](#) catalogue** is a feasible and cost-effective approach, albeit the catalogue was built to host epidemiological datasets and cohorts, which does not fully cover HEREDITARY's data types. Moreover, the main downside of this method is the lack of compliance with the 1+MG Framework and GA4GH initiatives.

Alternatively, the flexibility that a self-hosted implementation of the [Maelstrom](#) toolkit offers is not to be underestimated. Each of their **open-source tools** fills a gap in the process of dataset harmonisation, integration, cataloguing, analysis and hosting in a federated manner. Although this approach would render well-rounded results, it would entail the high **technical overhead** of deploying a full harmonisation initiative (Rmonise), website (Mica), federated discovery and analysis (DataShield), and, likely, data hosting (Opal).

Based on the above and the project requirements, the **suggested low-friction approach** (see [Figure 1](#)) is:

1. If data transfer is allowed: submit data and metadata to EGA/FEGA.
2. Always publish dataset metadata to HIP as the means to create HealthDCAT-AP dataset records that can be harvested by data.europa.eu.
3. Optionally, when there is a study or publication, create a Zenodo and BioStudies record that links to the EGA dataset(s), HIP entry, and any other artefacts.
4. For federated discovery, expose a Beacon-v2 endpoint where applicable (i.e., genomic datasets).

Figure 1. Overview of suggested approach: (1) submission of sensitive data and metadata to EGA; (2) submission of non-identifiable metadata to the HIP; (3) addition of high-level study/dataset metadata to BioStudies and Zenodo; and (4) deployment of queryable Beacons.

This approach aligns with T3.6's FAIR objectives, especially discoverability. Furthermore, it matches the project constraints around EU compliance and the mixed data-sharing policies across partners.

Additionally, the Hereditary Data Network (HDN)^{153,154} is under development and will take into account the inputs from this document. For example, using the EGA to find datasets, and be interoperable with Beacon-v2. See more details in D3.2.

Finally, although FAIRsharing¹⁵⁵ was not considered a dataset portal in this landscaping, it is clearly complementary: by registering the HEREDITARY standards and polystore as a resource, the project can increase the visibility of its data

¹⁵³ <https://github.com/mircocazzaro/tdn-endpoint>

¹⁵⁴ <https://github.com/mircocazzaro/central-tdn>

¹⁵⁵ <https://fairsharing.org>

infrastructure and demonstrate alignment with community standards, even if this does not directly enhance dataset-level findability [14].

6. Conclusion

We propose two submission routes (EGA/FEGA and HIP), a federated discovery (Beacon v2), and dataset- and study-level envelopes (Zenodo and BioStudies).

This mix gives the project broad coverage with minimal extra build: (1) EGA/FEGA handles archival and access of sensitive data; (2) HIP keeps the project datasets EHDS-compatible and ready for harvest by other aggregators; (3) Beacon enables federated discovery without centralising data; and (4) Zenodo/BioStudies improve citation and context by aggregating the project's datasets and their artefacts via links. All five are standards-based, well-documented, and integrated with EU/GA4GH/1+MG ecosystems.

7. Conflict of interest

The author of this report are part of the European Genome–phenome Archive (EGA) team at the European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI).

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